

EU LEADERSHIP IN SCHOLAR'S DIGITAL COMPETENCIES ADVANCEMENT

Society is entering an era where data shapes a new reality that is intangible but evident and objective. Digital technologies make it possible overcome physical barriers, and data contain evidence of human life, culture, and values. Uncovering and sharing the new knowledge data brings is a way toward a sustainable future (Lagoudakis et al., 2022; Tavares et al., 2022; Trabucchi & Buganza, 2018). Science and innovation are called to lead this digital transition and thus need to transform themselves (Ayrís et al., 2018; Bahrke & Grammenou, 2020; European Commission, 2020a, 2020b). This brings a new agenda on future science and education performance: high-quality (utilising lots of data), transparent, accessible, and reproducible research supporting data-driven decision-making and citizen science. Open Science (OS) practices, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management, digital content creation and sharing, and web visibility have become the core of modern Digital Scholar's competencies (Lagoudakis et al., 2022; Van Petegem et al., 2021; Weller, 2018; Winek, 2017). The European Union (EU) demonstrates leadership in recognising and addressing this challenge through the development of the EU DigComp 2.2 Framework (Vuorikari et al., 2022) and Open Science initiatives contributing to the development of common standards for digital competencies for scholars across the EU. Digital competencies are essential to enable the Open Science future. The need to integrate digital competencies training into scholar professional development programs is highly recognised (EU DGRI, 2017, 2020; EU DGRI & EOSC EB, 2021). The EU Open Science initiative and related resources can help scholars develop competencies using specific digital tools and platforms for data management, analysis, creation, and communication of research output. Promoting this experience and its adaptation in different national contexts is an opportunity to spread EU values, facilitate intercultural scientific communication and dialogue, and strengthen EU leadership in science and innovation to foster sustainable transformations.

In recent years, the Ukrainian science and education sector has faced several challenges, including limited funding, weak institutions and policy, and demographic issues. War has aggravated these problems. Despite this, many Ukrainian scholars make essential contributions to different fields, pushing EU-targeted change in research culture. Nowadays, the latter is in a state of transition: international collaboration and OS practices are of growing focus (KMU, 2022b, 2022a), but there is still a need to improve the overall quality of research and increase the impact of research on society. The EU's experience in digital competencies enhancement guiding these transformations will ensure a successful move towards an innovative and sustainable European future.

To enable a successful society's digital transformation, scholars are called to be leaders and mentors demonstrating high digital competency and adopting OS culture. Middle and senior-stage academic staff should act as catalysts of research culture changes meaning they should have advanced digital knowledge and skills (EU DGRI, 2017). Implementing digital competencies training in scholars' lifelong professional development programs is significant and urgent (EU DGRI & EOSC EB, 2021, c. 32). This also puts on the agenda the assessment of digital competencies and needs (Cabero-Almenara et al., 2021; Dias-Trindade & Albuquerque, 2022; EU DGRI, 2020; Suyo-Vega et al., 2022). Existing studies in the EU (Cabero-Almenara et al., 2021; Dias-Trindade & Albuquerque, 2022; EU DGRI & EOSC EB, 2021) have revealed the insufficient level of academic staff digital competencies. They have outlined the main bottlenecks and pushed a discussion on the scholars' professional training improvement and the digital competencies' lifelong learning perspective (EU DGRI, 2017). These studies provide a good reference and experience to adapt.

In Ukrainian HEIs digital knowledge and skills of academic staff are insufficient. This is rooted in the low research culture in HEIs of the Soviet period and the lack of systemic reforms under the background of the HEIs role transformation (Yegorov, 2009). Currently, at least 25 % of the annual workload of HEI's academic staff must be devoted to scientific work, and scholars are obligated to publish papers in high-quality international journals. However, this transformation was rather a "drift" (Hladchenko et al., 2018), and its results are tangible and threatening. A poor research culture, insufficient foreign language knowledge, and low adoption of digital technologies limit the internationalisation potential and deepen the gap between current knowledge and the training content, often based on outdated information (KMU, 2022a; Petrushyna, 2018). In 2015 experts rated the Ukrainian HEI scientific performance at an average of 2.4 points out of 5. The share of citizens who believe that national science lags behind the world's increased from 61% to 69 % for 2008–2015 (Petrushyna, 2018).

One should note that updating training programs supported by international initiatives have occurred recently. Such advanced training programs are mainly devoted to PhD students and young scientists. At the same time, the average age of academic staff in HEIs varies from 37.4-49.3 years (assistants and senior teachers) to 53.3-66.4 years (associate professors and professors) (Skyba, 2020), meaning most active staff are only superficially familiar with modern research practices. Without having proper up-to-date skills, it's not possible to conduct high-quality research and produce relevant output. Publication activity patterns could be a marker of this: even in leading universities listed in international rankings, the number of Scopus-indexed publications per one person over five years varies from 1.06 to 1.96, and citations - from 2.02 to 5.99 (Skyba, 2020). Ukrainian science is dominated by research of a theoretical nature (for example, in economics) (Mryglod et al., 2021). The introduction of new assessment and

scholar recognition regulations led to an increase in publications in predatory journals (1% on average and 22.63% in social sciences in 2019) and local Scopus journals (31,8% of total Scopus publications in 2019) (Hladchenko, 2022).

The lack of appropriate professional development training and “digital competencies and needs map” is the main obstacle to developing favourable policy facilitating EU vision-aligned science and education leadership over digital and sustainable transformations. Promoting OS knowledge, assessing needs, and providing Ukrainian scholars with digital competencies training based on EU practices, resources, and tools, makes it possible to meet the digital transformation challenge in Ukraine.

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